
SECURITY AWARENESS AND SAFETY MANAGEMENT AMONG PRIVATE SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined the extent to which security awareness predicts safety management among private school Principals in North-East Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. One objective was stated, one research question was raised and one null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. The Correlational research design was used for the study. The study population consisted 4179 teachers, 157 principals and 314 Vice principals in government approved private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom North-East senatorial. The sample for the study was 654; made up of 79 principals, 157 Vice principals and 418 teachers from 125 private secondary schools that were selected using the multi-stage sampling approach. Two sets of researcher developed instruments were used for data collection; these include “Security awareness Questionnaire (SAQ) which was designed for principals and Safety Management Questionnaire (SMQ) which was designed for the teachers. The reliability of the instruments was determined using inter-item method. Cronbach Alpha Analysis was used to obtain the reliability indices of .86 and .97 for the SAQ and SMQ respectively. Simple Regression Statistics was used for answering research question and testing the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Finding of the study revealed that principals’ awareness of school safety significantly predicts safety management of campus security. It was concluded based on the findings that principals’ security awareness predicts safety management among private school principals in North-East Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. It is recommended amongst others that principals should intensify efforts at routine checking on school physical infrastructure in order to guarantee they are safe and in good condition for use.

Keywords: Security Awareness, Safety Management, Private School Principals, North-East Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State

Introduction

Safety is the state of being free from hazard, risk, threats, injuries and loss of properties. School safety is seen as a situation in which the teachers and learners feel at home, develop confidence, maintain a positive state of mind, and do not show any signs of apprehension of withdrawal from the school, but work towards the achievement of their personal goals (Ogbo *et al*, 2021). Safety is seen as a situation where students and educators are not exposed to any form of danger or risk of physical or moral aggression, accident theft or deterioration. School safety is essential in all ramifications for efficient and effective academic pursuit, because teaching and learning cannot take place where fear, anxiety and suppression exist. Schools that are safe and responsive have plans and procedures in place to deal with violent and disruptive behaviours that may occur (Ronoh, 2018).

Safety management are means of preventing crisis, and reacting to violations of existing rules that prohibit bad behaviour which is likely to cause safety risk. Ssekamanya *et al.* (2016) asserted that a well-functional school is not only one that promotes learning, but also attends to safety of personnel and available facilities. Safety management describes the use of different strategies and available resources to protect staff, students and facilities from psychological and physical dangers. It is also a means of ensuring that administrators, teachers, students, parents, visitors and facilities in educational organization are free from danger, threats and destruction. One of the perspectives to safety management in schools involve the principal ensuring that school personnel obey rules and regulations, read meaning to sign post and labels on chemicals, wear safety gadgets, have fire extinguisher in classrooms and laboratory, observe road signs and highway code, among others (Hamilton-Ekeke, 2017).

The perception of insecurity or fear of violence has often influenced peoples' behaviour. This fear can affect learner's school attendance, cause poor school performance and the general poor administrative performance of the school principal. The researcher has observed that some private secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State do not seem to have physical security gadgets like fire detection system for fire prevention and good lighting system to prevent security breaches in the schools. This unfortunate situation has increased the call for adoption of safety management practices in schools. However, the level of adoption of these safety management practices by secondary school principals in North-East Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State is not clearly known. Hence, this study considers some security awareness in the school which can ensure safety in private secondary schools in the state.

Awareness is the ability to directly know and perceive, to feel, or to be cognizant of events. More broadly, it is the state of being conscious of something. Security awareness is the knowledge and attitude members of an organization possess regarding the protection of their physical, and especially informational, assets. In the School organization, security awareness can be created by introducing education courses on the prevention of emergencies, as well. Creating a safe environment starts with awareness of that environment. Teaching students how to identify issues before they become big problems goes a long way toward helping create a safe school environment.

It is generally accepted that a secured school is sine qua non to effective teaching and learning (Prinsloo, 2015); and that it is the most important characteristics of an effective school. Students and staff need a safe environment for academic, administrative and social activities. A standard security plan for campuses would include access control system, intrusion detection system, burglar alarm system, video surveillance and security

communication system (Christopher, 2018). Management of campus security involves the use of security and surveillance programmes to prevent crime and promote safety (Gottfredson and Gottfredson, 2020). This means that the school can make use of security guards or police officers, metal detectors, surveillance cameras, duress alarms, visitor sign-in/out procedures as various strategies to achieve a safe school.

Despite the importance of school safety management, there seems to be an upsurge in violent incidence in schools. It is expected that secondary school principals and members of the school management should be alert at all the time to prevent occurrence of acts of hooliganism so as to avoid blames for professional negligence. In some schools, there have been cases of senseless destruction in form of riots, burning, maiming, raping or even killing those they think are harsh on them (Usman, 2016). Ojo (2016) reported that some students go to school with jack knives, battle axes and even locally made guns to threaten and bully others. These problems do not only endanger students and teachers' lives but they also prevent teachers from concentrating on teaching and students from learning. The situation has spiraled to the incidents of extortion, rape, bullying and kidnapping resulting to high security threats. This insecurity instances have infused fear, tension, anxiety, uncertainty, grief into the principals. This has become a problem. It is against this background that this study sought to investigate how security awareness predict safety management practices among private schools principals in North-East Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

Safe schools are considered as very paramount to the attainment of educational aims and objectives through the imparting of the requisite skills, knowledge, values and attitudes to students in schools. This is usually attained where the students learn and the teachers teach in an environment free of fright. However, it seems secondary schools are no more safe in North-East Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State due to the incessant horrific attacks, cases of senseless destruction in form of riots, burning, maiming, and rape in schools. Meanwhile, principals have the primary duty to safeguard the students and staff in their care, while at the same time creating the security awareness. This objective seems not to be realised, as no study known to the researcher has been carried out in this direction. This unfortunate situation has increased the call for safety management of the school by principals such as management of campus security, which may curb the menace of insecurity and make secondary schools safe for teaching and learning. However, the level of safety management by private secondary school principals in Akwa Ibom North East is not clearly known. It is against this background that this study seeks to establish whether Security awareness predicts safety management practices among Private schools Principals in North-East Senatorial District in Akwalbom State.

Purpose of the study

The study seeks to determine the extent to which principals' security awareness predicts safety management of campus security in private secondary schools.

Research Question:

To what extent does principals' security awareness predict safety management of campus security in private secondary schools?

Research Hypothesis:

The extent to which principals' security awareness predicts safety management of campus security in private secondary schools is not significant.

Concept of Security Awareness

Security has been defined as the degree of protection against danger, damage, loss and crime. Orpinas *et al.* (2003), Van Jaarsveld (2011) defined security as a form of protection where a separation is created between the assets and the threat. Thus, security is the precaution taken to safeguard an environment from impending danger or injury. School security is the establishment and maintenance of protective measures that ensure a state of inviolability from hostile act or influences (Aryu, 2000). It is the level of awareness on security measures that can be taken to keep the school safe. Security measures can also be seen as approaches that can be adopted to protect and manage school so as to mitigate violence, reduce security risks, and ensure that the school environment is safe for teaching and learning (Laura, 2014). Secondary school principals can adopt a combination of human, physical and technological security measures to create a stable and fairly predictable school environment which is free from threat, harm or danger.

Principal security awareness also involves the implementation of multiple interdependent layers of security system that can include protective barriers, perimeter fence and other systems designed to protect persons and property. Principals of secondary schools can adopt physical security measures to ensure the safety of lives and property. When physical security measures are appropriately implemented, maximum protection will be guaranteed. According to Alimba (2018), some of the physical security measures that can be adopted by principals are the use of fence, locks and keys, safe and strong rooms, burglary proof, electronic equipment, among others. These security gadgets should be strategically fixed in places where the school management can easily use them to control and monitor people so as to prevent intruders from gaining access to such places.

Principal awareness of Technological security measures involves the application of tools and technical knowledge for the furtherance of security and promotion of safety in the school. It involves the application of security technologies to prevent and reduce violence, crimes, and risks in order to promote security and safety. The aim of using security technologies is to reduce opportunities to commit crimes or violence, to increase the likelihood that someone will get caught and to be able to collect evidence of some of the acts of violence being committed, thus making it easier to prosecute (Van Jaarsveld, 2011). The provision of security technologies such as CCTV surveillance system, protective lighting, alarm system, motion detectors in schools will help to reduce a good number of threats, risks and crimes that often occur in the school. It is advisable, that principals of secondary schools adopt the combination of human, physical and technological security measures in order to effectively manage safety in their schools.

Safety Management

Safety is the state of being free from hazard, risk, threats, injuries and loss of properties. Obiamaka and Enyi (2020) defined safety as a situation where students and educators are not exposed to any form of danger or risk of physical or moral aggression, accident theft or deterioration. Safety management refers to the means and ways of ensuring that administrators, teachers, students, parents, visitors and facilities in educational organization are free from danger, threats and destruction. Safety management measures in schools involve obeying rules and regulations, reading meaning to sign post and labels on chemicals, laboratory equipment, wearing safety gadgets, having fire extinguisher in classrooms and laboratories, observing road signs and highway code, etc. (Hamilton-Ekeke, 2017). The security of the school premises is an important part of ensuring safety of school personnel.

In a British Broadcasting Cooperation (2021), it was revealed that more than 30,000 alleged crimes linked to schools were reported to police in America and many other countries in the world. School security is unique in several ways. It serves not only to keep unwanted visitors out of the school but also to keep staff and students safe inside the school building. Security in schools has never been as important as it is now. In US over 74% of education related threats were recorded in middle schools, junior high, and high schools. Due to safety threats, during the 2013-2014 school year, reports say 93% of public schools installed locks or monitor doors and gates as a means of controlling access to the school (National Center for Educational Statistics (NCES, 2018). According to Umar and Umar (2022) school safety can be taken in a narrow way, if safety and securities in education are linked to eliminating physical harm. Yet an extensive interpretation reveals all risks concerning learners' welfare as a safety/security matter. Violence by young people is one of the most visible forms of violence. Both fatal and non-fatal assaults involving young people contribute greatly to the global burden of premature death, injury and disability. Youth violence deeply harms not only its victims, but also their families, friends and communities (WHO 2004).

Design of the Study

The study adopted a correlational research design. This design was used because it describes the relationship that exists between two variables, the strength and direction of the relationship without manipulating them.

Area of the Study

The research was carried out in Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of 4179 teachers, 157 principals and 314 Vice principals in government approved private secondary schools in Akwalbom North-East senatorial (Statistics Division of the State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size of principals was 79, representing 10 % of the population of principals. The sample size of vice principals was 157, representing 50 % of the population of vice principals. The sample size of teachers was 418, representing 10 % of population of teachers. This led to a total sample size of 654 respondents. Multistage approach was used in the study. At first, cluster sampling technique was used to cluster the Senatorial District into nine Local Government Areas. Then proportionate sampling was used to determine the number of schools to be selected that is, 18% of 157 private schools in the 9 LGAs which gave 26 schools. Proportionate sampling approach was used in selecting 418 teachers representing 10% of their population. Simple random sampling technique of hat and draw method was used for selecting the 26 private secondary schools and teachers in the area.

Instrumentation

Two sets of researcher developed questionnaire were used. They are: Security awareness Questionnaire (SAQ) for Principals and Safety Management Questionnaire (SMQ) for Teachers to respond. The SMQ contained 25 statements designed to gather information from teachers on how campus security is managed in their schools. The SAQ comprised of 15 statements measuring principals' awareness of security in the school. Both instruments were measured using a four point rating scale with response categories of: SA= Strongly Agree = 4 points, A = Agree = 3 points, D = Disagree = 2 points, SD = Strongly Disagree = 1 point for positively worded questions. SA= Strongly Agree = 1 points, A = Agree = 2 points, D = Disagree = 3 points, SD = Strongly Disagree = 4 point for negatively worded questions.

Validation of the Instruments

To ensure face validity of the two research instruments, the draft of the instruments, which contained 40 items was submitted to three independent validates for scrutiny and constructive criticisms.

Reliability of the Instrument

In order to establish the reliability of the instruments, the instruments were administered on randomly selected 20 respondents who were not selected for the study. Having administered the SAQ and SMQ once to the principals and teachers respectively, collected data were subjected to the reliability test using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. Cronbach Alpha method was used for the analysis because it was considered best for aggregate scores or instrument with multiple items (Ogbazi and Okpala, 1994). The reliability index of .86 and .97 were obtained for the SAQ and SMQ. Wells and Wollack (2003) noted that Cronbach's alpha ranges from 0 to 1.00, with values close to 1.00 indicating high consistency. Professionally developed high-stakes instrument should have internal consistency coefficients of at least .90. Lower-stakes instrument should have internal consistencies of at least .80 or .85. For a classroom exam, it is desirable to have a reliability coefficient of .70 or higher. Therefore, the reliability for this study was considered reliable enough.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered the instruments with the help of two research assistants. In doing this, the researcher briefed them on the approach to the respondents, such as distribution and collection of instrument. The completed instruments were then collected for collation of scores and analysis. The exercise lasted for two weeks.

Method of Data Analysis: Simple Linear Regression Statistics was used to answer the research question and to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. In answering the research questions, the decision rule by Condouris *et al.* (2003) was used to show the extent of prediction between the two variables. While in testing the null hypothesis, the F-calculated was compared with F-critical at 0.05 level of significance.

Decision Rule: According to Evans in Condouris, Meyer and Tager-Flusberg (2003), the following were used to determine the strength / extent of prediction. $\pm.00 - .19 =$ Very Low Extent; $\pm.20 - .39 =$ Low Extent; $\pm.40 - .59 =$ Moderate Extent; $\pm.60 - .79 =$ High Extent and $\pm.80 - 1.0 =$ Very High Extent

Results: The answer to research question and result of test of null hypothesis are presented below.

Research Question

To what extent does Principals' security awareness predict safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools?

Table 1: Simple Linear regression analysis for the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in private secondary schools

Variation	R	R ²	Extent of Prediction	Remark
Security Awareness	.778	.605	60.5 %	High Extent
Safety management of campus security				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The result in Table 1 shows the R for the strength of the relationship and R² for the determination of the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools. The R- Value of .778 indicates a high Extent of relationship between the two variables. The calculated R² of .605 which is the coefficient of determinant indicates that only 60.5% principals' Safety management of campus security is predicted or contributed by principals' security awareness. This implies that Principals' security awareness to a high extent, predicts Safety management of campus security.

Hypothesis: The extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in private secondary schools is not significant.

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Analysis for the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	F-crit	Decision (@P≤.05)
Regression	1614.151	1	1614.152	993.290	3.86	.000*
Residual	1054.662	649	61.625			
Total	2668.814	650				

* Significant at the 0.05 level of significance.

The entries in Table 2 revealed that the calculated F- Value of 993.290 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 650 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which states that the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools is not significant is rejected. The result means that the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools is significant. In other words, the Principals' security awareness is a significant contributor of Safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools.

Findings of the Study: The findings of this study show that:

1. Principals' security awareness to a high extent, predicts Safety management of campus security.
2. The extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts Safety management of campus security in Private secondary schools is significant.

Discussion of findings

Principals' Security Awareness and Safety Management of Campus Security

The findings of the analysis presented revealed that the extent to which Principals' security awareness predicts management of campus security in Private secondary schools is significant. This implies that for principals to manage their school security very well, they must be aware of the safety measures provided for school personnel. The reason for the outcome of this study is the fact that when the principal insists that perimeter fence be constructed round the school premises, ensure Collaborating with the police for rapid armed response services to the school, and there are security guards to monitor the school premises for improved school safety; these make them aware of the security of the school.

The finding of this study disagreed with the findings of Phaneuf (2006) who found that the use of selected security practices in schools did not influence levels of student fear or bonding. Again, the finding of this study agreed with the findings of Gottfredson *et al.* (2020) who found that many of the security and surveillance programmes were used more often in middle schools than in either elementary or high schools. They also reported that the use of several security measures (e.g., identification badges or cards, locating police or security personnel in the school, dogs, metal detectors, and inspection of books bags or purses) differed by location.

Conclusion

Based on the outcome of the study, it was concluded that principals' security awareness predicts safety management among Private schools Principals in Akwalbom North-East Senatorial District. It was also concluded that principals' awareness of school safety significantly predicts Safety management of buildings, water, school canteen, Fire safety and campus security in Private secondary schools in Akwalbom North-East Senatorial District.

Recommendations: Based on the finding and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Principals need to intensify efforts at routine checks on school buildings in order to guarantee that they are safe and in good condition for use.
2. Proprietors of schools should deploy paramilitary officers like civil defense, local vigilante officers to schools to mitigate the preponderance of social vices around the school premises and environment.

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